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THE TASKS OF STRATEGISTS IN THE BEHAVIOURAL
IMPLEMENTATION OF STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the tasks of strategists in the behavioral implementation of strategy and asserts that the future of strategy is leadership. It argues that the tasks of strategists in leadership positions should be rather seen and appreciated from the standpoint of the varied strategic leadership tasks at the beck and call of strategic leaders during turbulent times. Specifically, it posits that there are strategic leadership tasks that develop the personal and interpersonal qualities that become a strategist's motivational foundation while his / her leadership position lasted and, went further to propose that six strategic leadership tasks will take precedence over and above all other strategies. These are: [1] identification of the current enterprise position and deciding on a direction. [2] A review of the enterprise changing external world and internal company resources [3] Differentiated strategies of vision and mission. [4] Policies. [5] Leadership purpose and enterprise resources. [6] Industry leadership position. The paper argues that strategic leadership is not only important to the company or organization, but is also geared towards the overall development of the nation. The paper argues further that strategic leadership is a human factor, -which builds a group together and motivates them towards goal attainment. The paper contends that strategic leadership understands human problems and takes them into consideration in directing and managing employees for action. The paper argues further that besides leadership, there are other aspects of strategy implementation that have an

impact on the behaviour of strategists in implementing the chosen strategies. These, in the words of Kazmi (2005: 353), are: [1] Corporate culture. [2] Corporate politics and use of power. [3] Personal values and business ethics. [4] Social responsibility. The paper concludes that perhaps the single most important strategy for implementing the chosen strategies lies in motivating the organizational people you supervise by treating them the same way you wish to be treated: as responsible professionals irrespective of their hierarchical position in the organization.

Key Words: Tasks, Strategists, Strategy, Behavioural Implementation.

Introduction and Theoretical Underpinning

In the words of Kazmi [2005: 43], strategists are individuals or groups who are primarily involved in the formulation, implementation, and evaluation of strategy. In a limited sense, all managers are strategists. There are persons outside the organisation who are also involved in various aspects of strategic management. They too are referred to as strategists. Kazmi argues further that the CEO is the most important strategist who is responsible for all aspects of strategic management, from the formulation to the evaluation of strategy. As the chief strategist, the CEO plays a major role in strategic decision-making. During periods of turbulence and uncertainties, enterprises usually wonder aloud about the capabilities of their current strategies and, whether they would actually need a new strategy or not. Empirical evidence has shown that they do need it. If they do, the next question is how to come up with what they actually need a differentiated strategy. This is where the tasks of strategists become inevitable.

Hence the Rationale for this paper stems from the need to proactively develop a strategy that will address turbulent times whenever the occasion arises and, this is the stage where the strategists are called upon to intervene. Today, we are living in an environment that is highly competitive, cyber-motivated, change directed and, philosophically challenged. This environment which is a setter-forth of a set of economic, political and, sociological events in many countries has demonstrated a significant impact on the values and attitudes of any nation's work force and, has largely determined to a certain extent the kind of decisions managers make about the organisation's relationship with its strategy.

The weight of empirical evidence leans more on a factual scenario that the future of strategy is leadership. The real test of leadership lies in viewing it as an ongoing process." "The functions of leadership cannot be performed solely by occupying top positions but by exerting leadership in several areas. For instance, strategists are called upon to make a significant contribution towards developing an appropriate corporate culture, managing corporate politics, exemplifying personal values, and helping the organisation discharge its social responsibilities. All these tasks have to be performed in the context of behavioural implementation of strategy" [Kazmi, 2002: 357]. The late U.S. President, Dwight D. Eisenhower deposed in his life time that "Leadership is the art of getting someone else to do something you want done because he wants to do it."

This paper is divided into six parts: The first part of the paper addresses the future of strategy and argues that the tasks of strategists in leadership positions should be rather seen and appreciated from the standpoint of the varied strategic leadership tasks at the beck and call of strategic leaders during turbulent times. Concomitantly, the paper discussed six strategic leadership tasks that will take precedence over and above all other strategies in the behavioural implementation of chosen strategies.

The second part of this paper deals with the influence of corporate culture on the behaviour of strategists in implementing the chosen strategies. This is followed by the analysis of corporate politics and use of power. The fourth part of the paper discussed the Personal values and business ethics. While the fifth part of the paper concentrated on Social responsibility. The paper concludes that perhaps the single most important strategy for implementing the chosen strategies lies in motivating the organizational people you supervise by treating them the same way you wish to be treated: as responsible professionals irrespective of their hierarchical position in the organization.

The Future of Strategy and the Tasks of Strategists in Leadership Positions

In its ordinary everyday use, strategy can be defined as the means and how for accomplishing long term objectives. Strategy can also be defined as an integrated and coordinated set of commitments and actions designed to explore core competencies and gain a competitive advantage. It is a corporate blue print for action.

The above definitions demonstrate on the one hand that strategy is future-oriented, that is, anticipatory and consistent with long term trends and, on the other hand, it reflects a single strategic thrust with its different aspects having a common focus that are consistent with each other.

The military definition of a strategy is the art of applying logically all the aids, weapons and fighting forces that a country has at its disposal in time of war. Similarly, a health strategy can be defined as a course of action, specifying a selected mix of medical and/or health techniques, manpower, facilities, supplies and equipment for the achievement of major objectives. In this context therefore, the goal and the strategy constitute the whole strategic planning. Apparently, that is where the future of the organization lies and, that is where leadership is of critical importance. All managers at one time or the other make decisions in the organization but the aspect of making crucial and/or critical decision is the sole responsibility of leaders (strategists).

Furthermore, the quality of leadership throughout an organization clearly influences the overall health and vigour of such organization. Moreover, the placement of a group of persons and the activities they represent under a common leader provides the basic structural framework for the unified direction of such persons and their activities. Finally, since strategy intuitively appears to represent opposite extremes in a spectrum of possible leadership styles, it therefore concludes that the future of strategy is leadership. Concomitantly, this paper argues that the tasks of strategists in leadership position should be rather seen and appreciated from the stand point of the varied strategic leadership tasks at the beck and call of strategic leaders during turbulent times. In consonance with this the paper discusses six strategic leadership tasks that will take precedence over and above all other strategies in the behavioural implementation of chosen strategies. These are:

- a. Identification of the current enterprise position and deciding on a direction. The essence of this lies in the fact that the organization's internal capabilities and external circumstances constitute the bases of strategies formulated and implemented by organizations. Furthermore, since organizations are perpetually in contest with varied external circumstances as well as many internal strengths and weakness, it is therefore exigent that the current enterprise position must be identified in order to facilitate decision on a more possible and useful direction.

- b. A review of the enterprise changing external world and internal company resources. This is most desirable because of the iterative nature of the environment and the need to investigate and determine how well the present strategy is working, what strategic issues the company faces and, how strong is the company's competitive position.
- c. Differentiated strategies of vision and mission. The organization's vision is a pictorial representation, vis-à-vis a challenging portrait of the organizations' desired future; a picture of a future when the organizations goals are achieved and its mission accomplished. On the other hand, the organization's mission gives us at a glance why the organization exists in the first instance, its purpose and why, we do plans. Differentiation is based on quality and price and, its combination makes it nearly impossible for its competitors to take away its market share. What we do in the organization calls for establishing distinctiveness in product or service offering and would likely be attempted by concentration action. A thorough understanding and knowledge of the integration of vision and mission will lead to a better understanding of the reasons we are committed to the quality of life around us, as individuals and as a company and, the reason behind one's dedication to instructional dignity and our sense of responsibility to seek out better ways to serve.
- d. Policies-: are general guidelines, rules and procedure. Their nature is crucial in the life of the organization and they are of critical importance in guiding one's decisions collectively to reach one's stated goals and/or objectives.
- e. Leadership purpose and enterprise resources. The essence of this is to give credence and definition to the fit between the organization and its environment. Since no organization has unlimited resources, it therefore becomes appropriate to commit the organization to specific products, markets, resources and technologies over an extended period of time. Since strategies determine long-term competitive advantages, therefore the leadership purpose and enterprise resources must be appropriately defined so as to facilitate the implementation of formulated (chosen) strategies.
- f. Industry leadership position. This particular leadership strategy may be appropriate for an entity and is cost-effective. Gaining a leadership position will require one or more of the following:
 - o Aggressive price competition to purchase market share.

- Aggressive marketing to increase market share.
- Demonstrating to competitors a strong commitment to remain in the industry.

The paper argues that strategic leadership is not only important to the company or organization, but is also geared towards the overall development of the nation. In today's environment that is characterized by unpredictability, high risk and complex interpersonal dynamics, the act of leading others often feels like an impossible balancing act; that is, if the economy is good, budgets are robust, and employees are motivated and well paid. But this is far fetched a situation and there is no perfect situation in leadership, whether strategic or not. People are not factors of production; therefore both the leader and the people that are led must constitute a social unit in order to make the leadership meaningful. Therefore leadership must be characterized by relevant skills and techniques, vis-à-vis leadership styles that will motivate people being led and place their confidence on their leader and subsequently provide them with the much desired "locus standi" for excellent performance. Without leadership therefore, an organization would be only a confusion of people and machines.

Strategic leadership moves the organization forward and helps the organization attain the goals and objectives which it has stated for itself.

The paper argues further that strategic leadership is a human factor, which builds a group together and motivates them towards goal attainment. Managers plan, Organize and control the organizational activities. However, all these managerial functions will come to nought if managers lack the ability to lead people and to understand the human factor issues in leadership, at least to the extent of producing desired results.

The managerial function of leading according to Tannenbaum and Schmidt [1991:115] is defined as the process of influencing people so that they will contribute to organization and group goals. It is natural to find different organizations parading different objectives at different times. In the same vein, people working in the organizations also demonstrate different objectives at one time or the other: Organizations need people to attain organizational objectives and, similarly, people need organizations to attain their much desired individual objectives. It is in this capacity that effective leaders help these individuals to satisfy their aspirations and be able to function beyond the limits of their capabilities to contribute to organizational goals. Consequently, Tannenbaum and Schmidt [1991:115] posit that in the light of the foregoing, managers thus require an understanding of the roles assumed by people, the

individuality of people, and the personalities of people. The traditional management approach to leadership, which is consistent with Donald McGregor's Theory X denigrated and degraded the organizational people as if they are synonymous with factors of production. But gone are the days when that obnoxious approach held sway. Today, human dignity is highly upheld in almost every organization, for the undisputed fact that every organizational person has one thing or the other to contribute towards organizational goals and objectives.

The paper contends that strategic leadership should be taken into consideration in directing and managing employees for action. Leadership directs the activities and performance of an organisation. This is in line with both Thames [1998: 38] that saw leadership as "that communication behaviour of any individual (s) which activates a group toward its goal; and Mogaji (2006:111-115) that also saw leadership as "both a framework for getting things done satisfactorily in an organisation and the ability to find solutions to a problem anywhere at any time". These assertions justify leadership to be a critical factor of organizational performance.

The paper argues further that besides leadership, there are other aspects of Strategy implementation that have an impact on the behaviour of strategists in implementing the chosen strategies and, these are sojournd below.

- 1) Corporate culture.
- 2) Corporate politics and use of power.
- 3) Personal values and business ethics.
- 4) Social responsibility.

The paper concludes that perhaps the single most important strategy for implementing the chosen strategies lies in motivating the organizational people you supervise by treating them the same way you wish to be treated: as responsible professionals irrespective of their hierarchical position in the organization.

Corporate Culture

The phenomenon which often distinguishes good organizations from bad ones could be summed up as corporate culture. The well-managed organizations apparently have distinctive cultures that are, in some way, responsible for their ability to successfully implement strategies. Basically, organizational [corporate] culture is the personality of the organization. Culture is comprised of the assumptions, values, norms and tangible signs (artifacts) of organization members and their behaviors. It has been clearly demonstrated that every corporation has a culture (which often includes several subcultures) that exerts powerful influences on the behaviour of managers [Schwartz and Davis | 1982: 475 - 93] and Steiner, Miner and Gray [1982: 475 - 93]. Just as every organization has a culture, every organisation is ipso facto identified by a particular leadership style. It is the distinctive leadership style that provides the leverage and the locus standi by which the organizational culture and subcultures impact on the behaviour of strategists in implementing the chosen strategies. In the words of Newstrom and Davis [1997:205], "the total pattern of explicit and implicit leaders' action as seen by employees is called leadership style." It represents a consistent combination of philosophy, skills, traits, and attitudes that are exhibited in a person's behaviour. Each style also reflects, implicitly or explicitly, a manager's belief about a subordinate's capabilities [Theory X or Theory Y]. Leadership styles vary from one Organization to the other depending on the past experiences, qualities, personal convictions, inherited characteristics and environmental conditions. The concept of culture is particularly important when attempting to manage organization-wide change. Strategists and Practitioners are coming to realize that, despite the best-laid plans, organizational change must include not only changing structures and processes, but also changing the corporate culture as well. The cultural orientation of the people reflects the social interaction of a group of people in the society and, this is manifested in the psychographic lifestyle which the people bring along with them when they enter organizations.

Corporate Politics and Use of Power

Since organizations are a microcosm of the society in which they exist, it is therefore necessary to understand, the dynamics between corporate politics and the use of power. Sharplin (1985:141) states that Power is the ability to influence others and corporate politics is the carrying out of activities not prescribed by policies for the purpose of influencing the

distribution of advantages within the organization. To exercise power, a person, must have access to the decision-making caucus, and the amount of influence will depend on the opportunity to give advice, and the degree of joint decision-making which occurs. The concept of "power is central to understanding organizational life, because people devote much of their energies at work to trying to accomplish tasks either for themselves or on behalf of other people [Newstrom and Davis, 1997: 123] Newstrom and Davis proposed further that 'Politics' is seen as a way to manage situations where the various organization members bring different values to their work and consequently do not share meanings with each other.

Whilst accepting that 'political' behavior is inevitable, it can be argued that there are some forms of political behavior, which are unethical, and other forms which are acceptable.

Personal Values and Business Ethics.

Organisations have a duty to perform and, while directing all efforts towards the attainment of organizational objectives, strategists should not in any way sacrifice values and ethics at the altar of organizational goals. In consonance with this, organizations, in addition to all the strategies available for such exercises also make use of politics and power. Along this line, there is a tendency for strategists to over-shoot. In other words, the strategists might be tempted to use politics and power morally or amorally. This is where personal values and business ethics come into play, occupying centre stage in management. With the increasing restiveness and awareness of the international organizations such as the World Bank and IMF about ethical practices in business the twin issues of personal values and business ethics have become the concern of strategists in every well-managed organization in terms of implementing the chosen strategies.

Social Responsibility

Schermerhorn and Chappell (2000: 71) defined corporate social responsibility as "an obligation of the organization to act in ways that serve both its own interests and the interests of its many external stakeholders." Corporate social responsibility (CSR, also called corporate responsibility, corporate citizenship, responsible business and corporate social opportunity) is a concept whereby organizations consider the interests of society by taking responsibility for

the impact of their activities on customers, suppliers, employees, shareholders, communities and other stakeholders, as well as the environment. This obligation is seen to extend beyond the statutory obligation to comply with legislation and sees organizations voluntarily taking further steps to improve the quality of life for employees and their families as well as for the local community and society at large.
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Corporate_social_responsibility

Corporate social responsiveness is all about the conduct of relationships between business and its stakeholders. It's about doing business better through creating wealth of all types for all stakeholders, not just shareholders. Business relationships with stakeholders must be in harmony with prevailing societal values and answerable to universal ethical norms.

Conclusion

Apparently, the leadership technique for directing and motivating the people under your supervision, no doubt, lies with your leadership style. Therefore, in whatever capacity you find yourself leading, whether in private or public sector you are presiding over a group of people whose livelihood depends on your ability to provide adequately, a unified direction for them and the activities they represent. Your leadership style, therefore, has a direct impact on their performance effectiveness. Whether you work in a hospital, private practice, health maintenance organization, government facility, or university, you probably supervise other people. Your behavior as a manager has a direct impact on staff performance, productivity, satisfaction, and turnover: [Diane: Diane M. Fade.html]. This paper has examined the qualities of managers who motivate, thus providing proven techniques to inspire those who work with them. Leadership and its attendant problems have eventually led to premature retirement discharge, change of branch of personnel in the organization frequently. Nigeria's case is a very pathetic one in that over the years, it has been unfortunate not to have leaders of proven integrity (Obisi 1996:145-160).

The question is what is this concept called leadership that is generating a lot of concerns and interest among scholars and administrators? Martires and Fule [1993:112] asserted that as it is complex to understand or explain human behaviour, so it is also difficult to understand or explain leadership.

The paper concludes that perhaps the single most important strategy for implementing the chosen strategies lies in motivating the organizational people you supervise by treating them the same way you wish to be treated: as responsible professionals irrespective of their hierarchical position in the organization.

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